

MORPHOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL ASSESSMENT OF POST-RAINY SORGHUM GENOTYPES FOR SHOOT FLY RESISTANCE

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Abstract

The study aimed to investigate the morphological and biochemical parameters in post-rainy sorghum and their association with shoot fly resistance. Among the genotypes studied, RSV-2432 recorded maximum mean value for trichome density and lowest dead heart percentage, followed by RSV-2391. Both RSV-2432 and RSV-2391 exhibited better resistance to shoot fly infestation compared to Swarna and DJ-6514. It was recorded that the total soluble protein and chlorophyll content were found to be higher in susceptible genotypes Swarna and DJ-6514 as compared to resistant genotypes. Furthermore, enzymatic activities of polyphenol oxidase and peroxidase enzyme have been observed higher in the resistant parents than susceptible parents. This suggests that, plants having higher activity of peroxidase and polyphenol oxidase enzyme shows resistance mechanism.

In sorghum shoot fly resistance breeding program, using biochemical characters as marker traits can be a valuable strategy to broaden the genetic base and increase the level of resistance.

Keywords: Post-rainy sorghum, shoot fly, plant oxidative enzymes, protein, host-plant resistance

Introduction

Sorghum, scientifically known as *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench, is a valuable grass genus native to tropical regions. It holds the position as the fifth most significant cereal globally, following wheat, maize, rice, and barley (Dillon et al., 2007). Originating in Africa, Sorghum has since spread across various regions worldwide. It is referred to by different names such as great millet and guinea corn in West Africa, kafir corn in South Africa, dura in Sudan, mtama in eastern Africa, jowar in India, and kaoliang in China (Purseglove, 1972).

Sorghum is unique in its adaptation to extreme environmental conditions. In India, there are two distinct growing seasons for sorghum i.e. rainy (*kharif*) and post rainy (*rabi*) seasons. *Rabi* sorghum is highly valued for consumption purpose due to the excellent quality of the grain, which matures during rain-free cool climate. Hence, this grain fetches a high market price; almost double that of *kharif* grain. But the average productivity of *rabi* sorghum (953 kg/ha) is much less as compared to *kharif* sorghum (1018 kg/ha). The main reason for the low productivity of *rabi* sorghum is low genetic diversity and higher susceptibility to shoot fly. Therefore, there is a need to increase productivity by focusing on the development of improved shoot fly resistant lines.

Identifying sorghum varieties that possess stable resistance against shoot fly is of utmost importance as it can lead to a reduction in cultivation costs and the stabilization of yields. In India, around 32% of sorghum production is lost due to insect pests (Borad and Mittal 1983). Among the more than 150 insect pests that cause damage to sorghum from its early growth stages to harvesting, the sorghum shoot fly, *Atherigona soccata* (Rondani), is considered one of the most significant pests (Sharma 1993).

Host plant resistance (HPR) is an effective and cost-effective approach to control shoot fly populations in sorghum and does not require additional input costs for the farmer. The resistance to shoot fly in sorghum depends on various quantitative characters, and their combined expression determines the plant's resistance level. HPR is considered a sustainable, economical, and environmentally reliable method for managing shoot fly populations and it's essential to understand the mechanisms of resistance for developing insect-resistant sorghum varieties. This knowledge helps in identifying and utilizing resistant sources from germplasm effectively. Although there has been progress in identifying germplasm with resistance to shoot fly, there's still limited understanding of the physiological and biochemical mechanisms that confer this resistance. The present study aims to investigate the role of specific proteins and enzymes in *rabi* sorghum plants and their contribution to host plant resistance against shoot fly infestation. The study focuses on four key parameters viz., Total soluble protein (mg/g fresh weight), Total chlorophyll (mg/g), Polyphenol oxidase ($\Delta O.D./min/g$) and Peroxidase ($\Delta O.D./min/g$). These parameters were analysed among four genotypes from which two are resistant and remaining are susceptible for shoot fly.

2. Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out at Sorghum Improvement Project, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri, during the period *Rabi*, 2022 and material for present study was obtained from Senior Sorghum Breeder, Sorghum Improvement Project, MPKV, Rahuri. Four *rabi* sorghum genotypes were selected for the experiment, from which two shoot fly resistant viz., RSV-2432 and RSV-2391 and two shoot fly susceptible genotypes viz., Swarna and DJ-6514. For this study four different parameters were selected viz., Total soluble protein (mg/g fresh weight), Total chlorophyll (mg/g), Polyphenol oxidase (PPO)

(Δ O.D./min/g) and Peroxidase (POX) (Δ O.D./min/g). Analyses of these parameters were done among four genotypes from which two are resistant and remaining are susceptible for shoot fly.

The sorghum genotypes were planted in two rows. Each row having 4.5-meter length and the rows were spaced at 45 cm apart. The experiment followed a randomized block design with three replications. Normal agronomic practices were followed for cultivating the sorghum crop. Notably, no insecticide was applied in experimental plot. Overall resistance was recorded as the percentage of dead heart (DH %) and density of trichome caused by shoot fly infestation. Plants with dead heart were recorded in all plots at 28 DAE. (Ratio of the number of dead heart to the total number of plant \times 100) recorded at 28 DAE was used for evaluating resistance.

At 28 days after emergence (DAE), seedlings from each sorghum genotype were collected for biochemical analysis. Plant without dead heart symptom served as uninfested control. Soluble protein content in the seedlings was estimated using the method suggested by Lowry et al. in 1951. The enzyme extraction was done by following the procedure given by Kumar and Khan (1982) and enzyme activity was expressed as change in absorbance per minute per gram fresh weight (Δ O.D./min/g).

Results and Discussion

The genotypes differed significantly for all the characters, which indicated significant amount of variability present in the material selected for present investigation.

Morphological and Biochemical Performance of Genotypes for Shoot Fly Resistance

The mean values of two crosses Swarna \times RSV-2432 and DJ-6514 \times RSV-2391 for different characters of *rabi* sorghum have been presented in Table 3.1 and 3.2 and briefly discussed below.

Leaf glossiness (score)

Leaf glossiness is also important measurement of shoot fly resistance during seedling stage at 14 DAE. Resistance genotype RSV-2432 (1.87) and RSV-2391 (1.93) exhibited lowest mean value of leaf glossiness as compared to susceptible genotype Swarna (3.27) and DJ-6514 (3.67).

Trichome density (mm^2)

The mean value for trichome density recorded maximum in RSV-2432 (13.80) and minimum in Swarna (1.66). The genotype RSV-2391 (12.33) exhibited maximum mean value for trichome density as compared to DJ-6514 (0.27)

Leaf surface wetness (score)

Leaf surface wetness is one of the most important measurement of shoot fly resistance during seedling stage at 14 DAE was found minimum in resistance genotype RSV-2432 (1.80) and RSV-2391 (1.93) as compared to susceptible genotype Swarna (3.60) and DJ-6514 (3.53).

Dead heart percentage (%)

It was recorded that the genotype RSV-2432 least percentage of dead heart (16.11) followed by genotype RSV-2391 (18.33). RSV-2432 and RSV-2391 were resistant as compared to genotypes Swarna and DJ-6514 for shoot fly infestation, whereas the dead heart formation was greater on the genotypes Swarna and DJ-6514.

Based on the substantial information obtained from mean performance of genotypes, *viz.*, RSV-2432 and RSV-2391 can be considered in developing shoot fly tolerant hybrid.

Total soluble protein (mg/g fresh weight)

Total soluble protein was estimated more in the susceptible genotypes Swarna (2.42) and DJ-6514 (2.95) while lower in the resistant genotypes RSV-2432 (1.63) and RSV-2391 (2.18). From the analysis it was seems that after the infection of shoot fly, level of soluble protein increased and level increased activities were higher in the susceptible parents.

Total chlorophyll (mg/g)

Chlorophyll content was observed higher in susceptible genotypes Swarna (1.89) and DJ-6514 (2.45) while lower in the resistant genotypes RSV-2432 (1.52) and RSV-2391 (1.47). From the analysis it was observed that after the infection of shoot fly, total chlorophyll was higher in the susceptible parents as compared to resistant parents.

Polyphenol oxidase (PPO) (Δ O.D./min/g)

Results of enzyme activities shown in Table 3.1 revealed that the average polyphenol oxidase activities were higher in resistant genotypes RSV-2432 (0.37) and RSV-2391 (0.31) as compared to susceptible genotypes Swarna (0.26) and DJ-6514 (0.27). From these results, it was observed that activity of polyphenol oxidase increased after the infection of shoot fly.

Peroxidase enzyme (POX) (Δ O. D/min/g)

The average peroxidase activities ranged from 0.84 to 1.79 in susceptible and resistant genotypes. It was observed that activities of peroxidase enzyme increased after the infection by shoot fly and observed higher in the resistant genotypes as compared to susceptible genotypes. Highest value for peroxidase activity recorded by the resistant genotype RSV-2432, it means genotypes showing the resistance mechanism having higher activity of peroxidase enzyme

Table 3.1: Morphological parameters associated with shoot fly resistance in post-rainy sorghum

Sr. No.	Genotypes	Leaf glossiness (score)	Trichome density (mm^2)	Leaf surface wetness (score)	Dead heart percentage (%)
1.	Swarna (S)	3.27	1.66	3.60	36.00
2.	DJ-6514 (S)	3.67	0.27	3.53	75.56
3.	RSV-2432(R)	1.87	13.80	1.80	16.11
4.	RSV-2391 (R)	1.93	12.33	1.93	18.33

Table 3.2: Biochemical parameters associated with shoot fly resistance in post-rainy sorghum

Sr. No.	Genotypes	Total soluble protein (mg/g fresh weight)	Total chlorophyll (mg/g)	Polyphenol oxidase (Δ O.D./min/g)	Peroxidase (Δ O.D./min/g)
1.	Swarna (S)	2.42	1.89	0.26	0.84
2.	DJ-6514 (S)	2.95	2.45	0.27	0.85
3.	RSV-2432(R)	1.63	1.52	0.37	1.79
4.	RSV-2391 (R)	2.18	1.47	0.31	1.26

Plant resistance offers a promising approach for managing shoot fly because it is sustainable, economical and environmentally responsible. When developing insect-resistant crops, a thorough understanding of the underlying mechanism of the resistance is critical for formulating

optimal strategies for identifying and exploiting resistant sources. Although considerable progress has been made in identifying germplasm resistance to shoot fly, progress towards characterization of physiological and biochemical mechanisms conferring the resistance

remain limited. Thus the present study was carried out with an objective of detecting the role of protein and enzymes in *rabi* sorghum plant and their activity in host plant resistance to shoot fly infestation.

Total soluble protein was estimated more in the susceptible genotypes Swarna and DJ-6514 while lower in the resistant genotypes RSV-2432 and RSV-2391. The similar results were observed by earlier workers, Padmja *et al.*, (2014) who reported an overall increase in total protein content compared with uninfected plant in sorghum, Bhoge *et al.*, (2017) and Patil *et al.*, (2017) also reported similar findings in sorghum. The genotypes having lower chlorophyll content were less susceptible to shoot fly. The higher chlorophyll content led to susceptibility because of increased preference of shoot fly larvae towards the higher chlorophyll containing plant. Similar results were reported by Patil *et al.*, (2017), also reported significant differences for chlorophyll content among susceptible and resistant genotypes in sorghum. Results of enzyme activities were higher in resistant genotypes RSV-2432 and RSV-2391 as compared to susceptible genotypes Swarna and DJ-6514. It was observed that activities of enzymes increased after the infection by shoot fly and it has been earlier reported by Padmja *et al.*, (2014), Bhoge *et al.*, (2017) and Patil *et al.*, (2017).

Conclusion

The study's findings suggest that higher enzyme activity and protein content are associated with resistance in sorghum plants against shoot fly infestations. These biochemical traits can be used as markers in breeding programs aimed at developing sorghum varieties with increased resistance to shoot fly. By selecting for these traits, the genetic base of resistant sorghum can be broadened, potentially leading to more effective resistance against shoot fly pests.

In summary, this study contributes to our understanding of how plant biochemical traits, particularly enzyme activities and protein content, can play a crucial role in sorghum's resistance to shoot fly infestations. These findings may have practical applications in breeding programs to develop more resilient sorghum varieties.

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